

A Comparative Study of the Tool Life Equations for Tungsten Carbide against Steel Turning Process

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to provide and enhance Taylor's tool life equation to provide more accurate and comprehensive tool life prediction model that can be universally applied to various cutting materials by matching the real time machining tool life with the equational tool life value. The proposed Taylor's tool life equation integrates parameters such as cutting conditions, tool material properties and work piece material characteristics to provide a thorough model for predicting tool life span accurately. By adding other variables, exponents, gathering the data and validating it, this study demonstrates the efficiency of Taylor's tool life equation. This research aims to provide and enhance Taylor's Tool Life Equation to provide a more accurate and comprehensive tool life prediction model that can be universally applied to various cutting materials by matching the real time machining tool life with the equational tool life value and achieved the approximate results.

Keywords: Taylor's tool life equation, Tool life.

1. Introduction

Metal turning processes are integral to manufacturing operations, influencing the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of machines. The accuracy of tool life predictions is paramount for optimizing these processes. However, the widely used Taylor's tool life equation, a staple in machining studies, reveals limitations as it neglects to consider flank wear, a critical factor influencing tool performance[1]. This oversight introduces inaccuracies in tool life predictions, hindering the selection of optimal cutting tools for diverse materials. Taylor's tool life equation, developed by Frederick W. Taylor, is a fundamental concept in machining and manufacturing engineering. Taylor conducted extensive research in the late 19th and early 20th centuries to understand the relationship between cutting speed, tool life, and other machining parameters[2]. His groundbreaking work laid the foundation for modern machining practices and optimization techniques.

Taylor's tool life equation relates the cutting speed (V), tool life (T), and various constants (n, C) using the equation $V \cdot T^n = C$. His equation suggests that the product of cutting speed raised to a certain power and tool life remains constant under certain machining conditions[3]. Taylor derived this equation through empirical studies, where he systematically varied cutting speeds and observed the corresponding tool life. By plotting experimental data and analyzing the trends, Taylor deduced that the relationship between cutting speed and tool life was power-law[4]. The exponent n in the equation represents the rate at which tool life changes with cutting speed. Overall, Taylor's tool life equation revolutionized machining practices by providing a quantitative framework for optimizing cutting speeds and tool life[5]. It remains a cornerstone in machining theory and continues to influence modern manufacturing processes and tool design methodologies. Metal turning processes are integral to manufacturing operations, influencing the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of machines[6]. The accuracy of tool life predictions is paramount for optimizing these processes but the commonly utilized Taylor's tool life equation, a staple in

machining studies, reveals limitations as it neglects to consider flank wear, a critical factor influencing tool performance. This oversight introduces inaccuracies in tool life predictions, hindering the selection of optimal cutting tools for diverse materials.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Tool material: Tungsten carbide

Atoms of tungsten (W) and carbon (C) combine to form the composite material known as tungsten carbide. It is a thick, hard substance with remarkable strength, wear resistance, and hardness that is perfect for a variety of industrial uses, especially in abrasives, cutting tools, and wear-resistant parts. In industries where hardness and durability are crucial, such as machining, mining, drilling, and metalworking, tungsten carbide is frequently utilised.

2.2 Workpiece material: P3 steel 4140 / 42 cr M04 /1.7225

P3 steel 4140, also known as 42CrMo4 or 1.7225, is a versatile chromium-molybdenum alloy steel commonly used in engineering applications

3. Experimental procedure

3.1 Extraction of data from real time machining process

The data is extracted from real time machining as shown in the figure1. The operation took by using tungsten carbide inserts and performed turning operation on Steel material.

Fig.1. CNC Lathe used for the operation.

Fig.2.Turning Operation on the cylindrical steel bar

The table 1 shows different variations in tool life with a different cutting speed, Including the feed and depth of cut.

Table 1: Test Data includes Speed, Feed, Depth of cut and Tool Life

Speed in rpm	Feed in mm/rev	Depth of cut in mm	Tool life in min
225	0.40	1.50	24.17
135	0.40	1.50	54.70
225	0.25	1.50	47.26
135	0.26	1.50	80.15
180	0.30	1.50	76.22
200	0.45	1.50	29.70

3.2 Equation-1: Taylor's Equation $V.Tn=C$

In the above equation, we have found a method to calculate 'n' and 'c' which are the exponent and constant in the equation. By using statistical method of calculation, we have obtained very close results using cutting speed 225 (m/min) as it is said that if the speed increases tool life decreases. The result of the equation is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Result Table

Cutting speed (m/min)	Experimental tool life(min)	Calculated Tool life(min)	Deviation
135	54.70	55.98	1.28
200	29.70	28.905	0.8
225	24.16	24.56	0.4

Fig.3 Graph of Equation Experimental vs Calculated

3.3 Equation-2: Modified Taylor’s Equation - $V \times T^n \times F \times D = C$

In this equation, we tried to incorporate variables like feed (F) and depth of cut (D), by using slope equation and logarithmic form we found the value for the exponents and tool life we have obtained very close results using cutting speed 200 (m/min). The following results are shown in table 3.

Table 3: Result Table

Cutting speed (m/min)	Experimental toollife (min)	Calculated tool life (min)	Deviation
135	54.70	56.60	1.9
200	29.70	30.03	0.33
225	24.16	24.83	0.67

Fig.4 Graph of Equation Experimental vs Calculated

3.4 Equation-3: Extended Taylor’s Equation - $T = (VC)M \times (AP)X.T \times (FZ)Y.T$

In this process we are eliminating Cutting velocity (Vc) and depth of cut (ap) and focusing on feed rate (Fz) to calculate the tool life, the modified equation used is $T = CT(FZ)Y.T$. The following results are obtained which are shown in

Fig.5 Graph of Equation Experimental vs Calculated

4. Results and discussions

In our pursuit to enhance tool life prediction models, we encountered a pivotal challenge: determining the exponent “ n ” in Taylor's tool life equation $V \times T^n = C$. While Taylor's equation provided a foundational understanding of tool life, so we have found out method to determine the “ C ” Through rigorous analysis and the application of logarithmic methods, we successfully devised a technique to ascertain the exponent n and constant C by substituting the theoretical values, the obtained tool life is 55.98 minutes theoretically, whereas the practically real time-tested tool life yields 54.70 minutes.

we explored an alternative method for predicting tool life, which involved integrating feedrate and depth of cut variables into the equation $V \times T^n \times F^{n1} \times D = C$ by incorporating these factors, we aimed to create a more comprehensive model for determining tool life and by substituting the theoretical values, the obtained tool life is 30.33 minutes theoretically, whereas the practically tested tool life yields 29.70 minutes.

We have even experimented by substituting the test data to the equation below

$V = C \times F^E \times A^F \times T^G \times VB^H$ and we have found out that the experimental data has more variation with the calculated data. by substituting the theoretical values, the obtained tool life is 304.95 minutes theoretically, whereas the practically tested tool life yields 54.70 minutes.

We have modified equation $T = \frac{C_T}{(V_C)^M \times (A_P)^{X.T} \times (F_Z)^{Y.T}}$ which is referred from Journal

to $T = \frac{C_T}{(F_Z)^{Y.T}}$

where we have Neglected cutting velocity and depth of cut with their exponents, by substituting the theoretical values, the obtained tool life is 58.26 minutes theoretically, whereas the practically tested tool life yields 56.3 minutes.

5. Conclusions

Finally out of all different equations collected from the research, we found that three equations are more relevant to the true value of tool life, as the other different equation which was found in the journals was not up to the accurate value of tool life, since we didn't have enough required data

6. References

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